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**The OSF genes within the DNA
of research data management
infrastructure**

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The OSF genes...

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RDM infrastructure

RDM infrastructure

Data Storage Finder

Data classification

- Low
- Medium
- High
- Very high

Data sharing

- Not needed
- With VU colleagues
- With anyone

Data volume

- < 500 GB
- > 500 GB

Features

- Basic storage
- Compute/HPC
- Collaboration tools
- Fine-grained access rights

OSF - Introduction

[Open Science Framework for Research Workflows - HumTech - UCLA](#)

OSF - Introduction

[The Open Science Framework \(cos.io\)](https://www.cos.io/)

OSF Institutions enhances transparency and increases the visibility of research outputs, accelerating discovery and reuse.

“Open Science aims to make the process of creating and sharing scientific knowledge more transparent, inclusive and equitable”

OSF VU

- 1010 Users
- 630 Projects
- 130 Preprints
- 12014 Files

The screenshot shows the OSF VU website interface. At the top, there is a dark navigation bar with the OSF logo and the text "OSFINSTITUTIONS" followed by a dropdown arrow. To the right of this bar are links for "Search", "Support", "Donate", "Sign Up" (in a green button), and "Sign In" (in a blue button). Below the navigation bar is a light gray header area featuring the VU logo (a blue bird) and the text "VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT AMSTERDAM". Underneath the logo is a line of text: "A Research Data Management Tool for the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Research Community | [VU OSF Getting Started Guide](#) | [VU Research Data Support](#) | [Contact RDM Support Desk](#) | [Join the VU OSF Advocates team](#)". Below this text is a search bar with the placeholder text "Enter search term(s) here", a magnifying glass icon, and a question mark icon. At the bottom of the screenshot is a horizontal menu with several tabs: "results" (highlighted in white), "Projects", "Registrations", "Preprints", "Files", "Users", and "Relevance".

OSF Faculties

OSF VU in years

VU OSF Users

VU OSF Files

Thank you!

Questions?